

Relative sensitivity of nano-mechanical cantilevers to stiffness and mass variation

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ABSTRACT

Investigating the relative sensitivity of nano-mechanical cantilever resonators to variations in stiffness and mass caused by adsorbates is essential. The analysis helps improve accuracy and stability as well as evaluating if undesired increases in mass and stiffness can be disregarded. A new dimensionless mathematical model based on the Rayleigh–Ritz method for studying the relationship between the relative sensitivity and related coupled parameters is proposed in this study. The results reveal that the geometric parameters of the cross-section tend to enhance the added bending rigidity more than the added linear density. The added stiffness and added mass exhibit precisely counteractive influences symmetrically to the cantilever's length axis centre. Commonly, the location of the adsorbate is more crucial than the cross-section property in determining the dominant factor between added stiffness and added mass. The model agrees well with both finite element analysis and experimental results. By identifying optimal adsorbate locations and bending modes, this model can enhance the accuracy and stability of measuring desired properties related to the Young's modulus and density of the adsorbate.

1. Introduction

Micro/nano-mechanical resonators have been widely applied in the measurement of mechanical and physical properties at the micro/nano-scale [1–6]. They have benefits such as being label-free, non-destructive [7], having ultra sensitivity [8–10], extreme temperature capability [11], and may be constructed into various structures like micro-tunnel resonators [12,13]. Their applications will be further extended with the development of micro-electro-mechanical system (MEMS) technologies [14–17]. They can measure adsorbates at micro/nano-scale with high precision [18–20]. Due to the versatility of mechanical resonators, they can be used to measure Young's modulus [21], density [6], bending rigidity [1–3], mass [10,22–26], rotary inertia [27], and the position of an adsorbate [4,5]. The unique capabilities of resonators, including precision, flexibility, and multi-functionality, render them highly suitable as sensors for a wide range of biological research applications involving cells [7,28], bacteria [18,29], viruses [30,31], and molecules [32,33]. It could be used to identify cancer cells from healthy cells and evaluate their cancer stage by measuring the Young's modulus of the cells [34]. Pujol-Vila et al. [35] detected bacteria and tested the susceptibility of antibiotics by using a mechanical resonator.

Mass detection studies have traditionally assumed that adsorbates can be treated as point masses, with their stiffness being negligible for cantilever resonators [4,5,18,36–38]. But the shapes of most samples

are not perfect balls, such as cells [7,39–42], polymer [6], and bacteria [35,43]. Besides, even cylinder adsorbates will introduce stiffness effects to cantilevers [2]. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the impact of the mass and stiffness of adsorbates on cantilever resonators. Certain scholars proposed that the natural frequency of resonators increases owing to the stiffness of adsorbates, while alternatively, a decrease occurs due to the mass of adsorbates [44,45]. Previous studies often focused on studying the mass and stiffness effects of adsorbates independently, in order to determine the optimal sensitivity for determining either mass or stiffness [46]. Xiang et al. [47] built a dimensionless model and studied the sensitivity of the cantilever resonator to the mass and stiffness of the adsorbate separately. However, there were limited mentions of the relative sensitivity of added stiffness to added mass of the cantilever in relation to adsorbate. Additionally, constructing a mathematical model to investigate the intricate correlation among these parameters, as well as devising a method to eliminate the undesired mass or stiffness effect of the adsorbate remained unexplored.

The excitation of high-order natural frequencies of resonators has been available with the development of technologies like optical thermal for high-speed excitation [45,48–50], and electrostatic capacitive actuation scheme for ultra-high frequency [51,52]. Resonator's higher-order natural frequencies can enhance the sensitivity to adsorbate

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Fig. 1. The schematic of a cantilever resonator with a cuboid adsorbate positioned on it. The first five bending modes of the resonator are studied. The length, width, and thickness of the cantilever resonator are L , W_R , and T_R , respectively. The adsorbate deposited on the surface ranging from x_s to x_e are assumed as a layer of length L_C , width W_C and thickness T_C . E_R , E_C , ρ_R , and ρ_C represent the Young's modulus and mass density of the cantilever and adsorbate, respectively.

parameters [53]. Moreover, more information can be decoded from the cantilever's dynamic vibration [45,54]. When the adsorbate is not optimally positioned, high-order natural frequency measurements can aid in determining its parameters. Dohn et al. [4] developed a method to determine the mass and position of an adsorbate on a cantilever using different bending mode natural frequencies. Ma et al. [22] conducted a study on measuring the mass of multiple particles utilizing the multi-order natural frequencies of a nano-mechanical cantilever plate. Belardinelli et al. [6] simultaneously measured Young's modulus and density of a polymer cube by combining the first and higher-order natural frequencies. These studies revealed the potential for enhancing measurement accuracy by incorporating higher-order natural frequencies. In order to gain a deeper understanding of the influence of adsorbate parameters on cantilever resonators, it is crucial to investigate their impact on high-order natural frequencies.

The measurement of natural frequency shifts in resonators has been employed to detect subtle variations resulting from changes in properties. This has been accomplished using methods such as quality factors [18] and amplitude-based sensing principles [55,56]. These techniques have been widely applied in resonator studies [57,58]. Furthermore, most of the computational methods using the frequency shift for resonator studies are based on the Euler–Bernoulli beam theory and the Rayleigh–Ritz method [4–6,59,60].

In this study, we have developed a non-dimensional mathematical model for nano-mechanical cantilever resonators using the Rayleigh–Ritz method. This model allows us to assess and quantify the effects of the additional stiffness and mass attributed to the adsorbate on the resonator. To validate the proposed method, finite element analysis (FEA) was employed, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of our findings. Furthermore, the experiments agreed well with the theory. This model can assist in identifying the optimal adsorbate placement to minimize the influence of undesired parameters. The dimensionless model offers the advantage of providing results applicable to both micro and nano mechanical resonator studies, accommodating a wide range of parameters for adsorbates and cantilever resonators.

2. Mathematical model and theory

The dimensionless mathematical model for studying the relative sensitivity of added bending stiffness and linear density of the cantilever based on the Rayleigh–Ritz method is developed. Firstly, the dimensionless natural frequency model for an adsorbate on a cantilever is built. Then, the mathematical model is developed to calculate the relationship between the linear density and the bending rigidity of the cross-section. Finally, the effects of adsorbate location and length on the cantilever for different bending modes are studied.

2.1. Dimensionless mathematical model of cantilever resonator with a cuboid adsorbate

The study focus on cuboid adsorbates and cantilevers, as they represent the prevalent shape employed in cantilever studies [3,5,6,22,44,47,60]. The schematic of a mechanical resonator model is shown in Fig. 1, which is a large length-to-thickness ratio cantilever and shaped as a uniform cross-section cuboid. The length, width, and thickness of

the cantilever resonator are L , W_R , and T_R , respectively. The Young's modulus and density of the cantilever are E_R and ρ_R . The x -axis is along the length axis of the cantilever, and the z -axis is along the thickness axis of the cantilever. The cuboid adsorbate is located on the top surface of the micro/nano-mechanical cantilever. The length, width, thickness, Young's modulus, and density of the adsorbate are L_C , W_C , T_C , E_C , and ρ_C , respectively. The location of the border of the adsorbate closest to the fixed end of the cantilever is denoted as x_s , while the furthest is designated as x_e . The centre position of the cantilever is represented by x_m . The relationship between x_s , x_m , x_e , and L_C can be written as $x_s = x_m - \frac{1}{2}L_C$ and $x_e = x_m + \frac{1}{2}L_C$.

The Rayleigh–Ritz method has been widely applied in the study of mechanical resonators [3–6,47]. To simplify the mathematical model while maintaining generality, certain assumptions have been made. The model assumes that both the adsorbate and resonator are composed of elastic isotropic materials. Additionally, it assumes that there is no mode shape change, rotatory inertia, damping [61], Poisson's ratio [62], or shear deformation of the cantilever or adsorbate. These simplifications allow for a more straightforward analysis of the system, focusing on the fundamental aspects of the mass and stiffness effects without the complexities introduced by these additional factors. The mathematical model of the vibration system is built based on the Rayleigh–Ritz method, the natural frequency of the cantilever resonator is given by

$$\omega_n^2 = \frac{\int_0^L D(x) \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Phi_n(x)}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 dx}{\int_0^L M(x) \Phi_n^2(x) dx}, \quad (1)$$

where ω_n is the n th order bending mode angular natural frequency of the vibration system consisting of the cantilever resonator and adsorbate. The bending rigidity and linear density of the cross-section are represented by $D(x)$ and $M(x)$, respectively. The n th order time-independent mode shape of the cantilever resonator is denoted as $\Phi_n(x)$, where x represents the axis along the length direction of the cantilever from the fixed end to the free end. The presentation of mode shape $\Phi_n(x)$ and the dimensionless form are shown in Appendix A.

The linear density $M(x)$ of the cantilever and adsorbate is dependent on the location of the adsorbate on the cantilever.

$$M(x) = \begin{cases} M_R = \rho_R W_R T_R, & 0 \leq x < x_s, \quad x_e \leq x \leq L \\ M_C + M_R = \rho_C W_C T_C + \rho_R W_R T_R, & x_s \leq x < x_e \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Similarly, the bending rigidity $D(x)$ of the bare cantilever can be calculated using the theory of material mechanics. The bending rigidity of the cross-section of bare cantilever D_R is given by

$$D_R = \frac{E_R W_R T_R^3}{12}. \quad (3)$$

When the cross-section only consists of the cantilever, the bending rigidity $D(x)$ remains equal to D_R . However, in cases where the cross-section includes both the cantilever resonator and the adsorbate, the bending rigidity $D_{R,C}$ can be calculated as [23,33,45]

$$D_{R,C} = \frac{E_C^2 W_C^2 T_C^4 + E_R^2 W_R^2 T_R^4 + E_C W_C T_C E_R W_R T_R (4T_C^2 + 4T_R^2 + 6T_C T_R)}{12 (E_C W_C T_C + E_R W_R T_R)}, \quad (4)$$

Table 1
The dimensionless parameters of the cantilever and adsorbate with their range.

Parameter	α	β	ζ	χ	ϵ	τ
Ratio	L_C/L	W_C/W_R	T_C/T_R	x/L	E_C/E_R	ρ_C/ρ_R
Range	(0, 1]	(0, 1]	(0, +∞)	[0, 1]	(0, +∞)	(0, +∞)

The detailed procedure to derive the formula $D_{R,C}$ is presented in Appendix A.

Thus $D(x)$ is defined as

$$D(x) = \begin{cases} D_R, & 0 \leq x < x_s, \quad x_e \leq x \leq L \\ D_{R,C}, & x_s \leq x < x_e \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

We constructed a dimensionless mathematical model using the Rayleigh–Ritz method to investigate how various parameters affect the natural frequencies of the bending modes of the resonator. Here, we utilize the ratio of various parameters of the adsorbate and cantilever, including length, width, thickness, location, Young’s modulus, density, and mode shape amplitude to describe their relationship. The ratios of these parameters between the adsorbate and cantilever resonator can be calculated as $\alpha = L_C/L$, $\beta = W_C/W_R$, $\zeta = T_C/T_R$, $\chi = x/L$, $\epsilon = E_C/E_R$, $\tau = \rho_C/\rho_R$. The relative position ratio such as χ_s , χ_m and χ_e follows the relationship $\chi_s = \chi_m - \frac{1}{2}\alpha$, $\chi_e = \chi_m + \frac{1}{2}\alpha$, and $\frac{\alpha}{2} \leq \chi_m \leq 1 - \frac{\alpha}{2}$. The dimensionless parameters and their ranges are presented in Table 1.

The natural frequency of the cantilever is influenced by various factors, including the additional bending rigidity and linear density of the cross-section, as well as the length and location of the adsorbate. Ω_n can be shown as

$$\Omega_n^2 = \frac{\int_0^1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2 d\chi + \int_{\chi_s}^{\chi_e} \eta \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2 d\chi}{\int_0^1 U_n^2(\chi) d\chi + \int_{\chi_s}^{\chi_e} \lambda U_n^2(\chi) d\chi} \quad (6)$$

where Ω_n represents the n th order dimensionless angular natural frequency of the cantilever and adsorbate by using the Rayleigh–Ritz method. λ represents the dimensionless additional linear density introduced by the adsorbate, while η represents the dimensionless additional bending rigidity of the cross-section contributed by the adsorbate. $U_n(\chi)$ is the dimensionless time-independent mode shape of the cantilever. The relationship between the natural frequency in dimensionless form and general can be calculated by substituting Eq. (6) into Eq. (1) and presented as

$$\Omega_n = \omega_n \sqrt{\frac{12\rho_R L^4}{E_R T_R^2}} \quad (7)$$

The dimensionless additional linear density, denoted as λ , can be determined by the following calculation

$$\lambda = M_C/M_R = \tau\beta\zeta \quad (8)$$

The dimensionless additional bending rigidity, denoted as η , can be expressed as follows

$$\eta = \frac{D_{R,C} - D_R}{D_R} = \frac{\epsilon^2\beta^2\zeta^4 + 4\epsilon\beta\zeta^3 + 6\epsilon\beta\zeta^2 + 3\epsilon\beta\zeta}{\epsilon\beta\zeta + 1} \quad (9)$$

After analysing the dimensionless natural frequency of the cantilever resonator with the adsorbate using the Rayleigh–Ritz method, the next step is to establish a methodology for independently evaluating the additional bending stiffness and mass.

The dimensionless natural frequency equation, denoted as Eq. (6), has been derived and presented. In order to isolate the effects of the added stiffness or mass of the adsorbate on the bare cantilever, we can extract the terms related to each factor separately from the equation. By utilizing this approach, we can determine dimensionless natural frequencies that are exclusively impacted by the added stiffness or mass, in addition to the natural frequencies of the bare cantilever. This

separation allows us to precisely analyse the individual influence of added stiffness and added mass on the overall natural frequency of the system.

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \Omega_{n,E}^2 &= \frac{\int_0^1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2 d\chi + \int_{\chi_s}^{\chi_e} \eta \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2 d\chi}{\int_0^1 U_n^2(\chi) d\chi} \\ \Omega_{n,M}^2 &= \frac{\int_0^1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2 d\chi}{\int_0^1 U_n^2(\chi) d\chi + \int_{\chi_s}^{\chi_e} \lambda U_n^2(\chi) d\chi} \\ \Omega_{n,0}^2 &= \frac{\int_0^1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2 d\chi}{\int_0^1 U_n^2(\chi) d\chi} \end{aligned} \right. \quad (10)$$

where $\Omega_{n,E}$ and $\Omega_{n,M}$ are the dimensionless angular natural frequencies of the cantilever only affected by the added stiffness and added mass of the adsorbate, respectively. $\Omega_{n,0}$ represents the dimensionless natural frequency of the bare cantilever without any adsorbate. The relationship between Ω_n , $\Omega_{n,E}$, $\Omega_{n,M}$, and $\Omega_{n,0}$ can be found in Eq. (10) and expressed as follows

$$\Omega_n = \frac{\Omega_{n,E} \cdot \Omega_{n,M}}{\Omega_{n,0}} \quad (11)$$

In order to investigate the impact of the added stiffness attributed to the adsorbate on the natural frequencies of the cantilever resonator, we formulated the following equation

$$\frac{\Omega_{n,E}^2}{\Omega_{n,0}^2} = 1 + \frac{\eta \int_{\chi_s}^{\chi_e} \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2 d\chi}{\int_0^1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2 d\chi} \quad (12)$$

where the function $\int_{\chi_s}^{\chi_e} \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2 d\chi / \int_0^1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2 d\chi$ is always greater than 0 for $\alpha > 0$. Since added dimensionless bending rigidity η is always greater than 0, it is easy to show that $1 \leq \Omega_{n,E}^2 / \Omega_{n,0}^2 \leq 1 + \eta$ for any order natural frequencies of the cantilever resonator. $\Omega_{n,E}^2 / \Omega_{n,0}^2$ will be the minimum value as 1 when the length ratio $\alpha = 0$. While when $\alpha = 1$, $\Omega_{n,E}^2 / \Omega_{n,0}^2$ will be the maximum value of $1 + \eta$. Theoretical analysis shows that the natural frequency of the cantilever resonator will always increase due to the added stiffness of the adsorbate. Similarly, we constructed the following equation to study the effect of the linear density of the cross-section on the natural frequency of the cantilever resonator as

$$\frac{\Omega_{n,0}^2}{\Omega_{n,M}^2} = 1 + \frac{\lambda \int_{\chi_s}^{\chi_e} U_n^2(\chi) d\chi}{\int_0^1 U_n^2(\chi) d\chi} \quad (13)$$

Similar to Eq. (12), the value of $\int_{\chi_s}^{\chi_e} U_n^2(\chi) d\chi / \int_0^1 U_n^2(\chi) d\chi$ will always be greater than 0 for $\alpha > 0$, and the added linear density ratio λ is always greater than 0. It can be shown that $1 \leq \Omega_{n,0}^2 / \Omega_{n,M}^2 \leq 1 + \lambda$ for any order of the natural frequency of the cantilever resonator. When the length ratio $\alpha = 0$, $\Omega_{n,0}^2 / \Omega_{n,M}^2$ will be the minimum value of 1.

While when $\alpha = 1$, $\Omega_{n,0}^2 / \Omega_{n,M}^2$ will be the maximum value of $1 + \lambda$. Theoretical analysis indicates that the adsorbate’s mass will inevitably lead to a decrease in the natural frequency of the cantilever resonator.

We built the mathematical model of G_n as follows

$$G_n = \frac{\left(\frac{\Omega_{n,E}^2}{\Omega_{n,0}^2} - 1\right)}{\left(\frac{\Omega_{n,0}^2}{\Omega_{n,M}^2} - 1\right)} = \frac{\eta \cdot g_{n,E}}{\lambda \cdot g_{n,M}} \quad (14)$$

where function G_n is defined as the relative sensitivity of cantilever resonators to the additional stiffness and mass due to the adsorbate. $g_{n,E}$ and $g_{n,M}$ are presented as follows

$$\begin{cases} g_{n,E} = \frac{\int_{x_s}^{x_c} \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(x)}{\partial x^2}\right)^2 dx}{\int_0^1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(x)}{\partial x^2}\right)^2 dx}, \\ g_{n,M} = \frac{\int_{x_s}^{x_c} U_n^2(x) dx}{\int_0^1 U_n^2(x) dx} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where $g_{n,E}$ represents the effect of dimensionless natural frequency of the cantilever resonator when the added stiffness of the adsorbate is taken into account, with $\eta = 1$. Similarly, $g_{n,M}$ characterizes the dimensionless natural frequency when considering the added mass of the adsorbate, with $\lambda = 1$. The values of $g_{n,E}$ and $g_{n,M}$ vary as the length and location of the adsorbate are changed.

If $G_n > 1$, the added bending stiffness of the adsorbate will take the key role. Furthermore, for $G_n \gg 1$, added stiffness dominate and make the effect of the additional mass negligible. Similarly, when $G_n < 1$, the added mass of the adsorbate will take the leading role, and for $G_n \ll 1$, added mass will dominate and make added stiffness negligible in the application.

2.2. The effect of geometric parameters on the additional bending rigidity and linear density of the cross-section

Based on the mathematical model, the additional bending rigidity and linear density depends on the dimensionless width, thickness, Young's modulus, and density. This section focuses on exploring the coupled impact of these parameters on the ratio of added bending rigidity to added linear density in the cross-section.

The functions of the added bending rigidity η and the added linear density λ exhibit a strong coupling, as they possess the same width and thickness ratio parameters. It is imperative to investigate the conditions under which either the added linear density or the added bending rigidity surpasses the other. By substituting Eq. (8) into Eq. (9), The ratio of added bending rigidity to linear density of the cross-section can be derived as

$$\frac{\eta}{\lambda} = \frac{\beta \epsilon^2 \zeta^3 + 4\epsilon \zeta^2 + 6\epsilon \zeta + 3\epsilon}{\tau (\beta \epsilon \zeta + 1)} \quad (16)$$

By making $\lambda = \eta$, the following equation can be shown to determine the τ/ϵ value that makes added linear density equal to bending rigidity.

$$\tau/\epsilon = \frac{\beta \epsilon \zeta^3 + 4\zeta^2 + 6\zeta + 3}{\beta \epsilon \zeta + 1} \quad (17)$$

In this case, bending rigidity η and added linear density λ share the same thickness and width. Here we constructed the equation f for further analysis. f represents the dimensionless ratio of added moment of inertia to the added area of the cross-section. The formula of f is given as

$$f = \frac{\beta \epsilon \zeta^3 + 4\zeta^2 + 6\zeta + 3}{\beta \epsilon \zeta + 1} \quad (18)$$

When $\tau/\epsilon > f$, the added linear density of the cross-section has a more significant impact, while when $\tau/\epsilon < f$, the variation of bending rigidity will be greater than that of linear density. In this scenario, we solve the equation for $f = 1$, which implies that τ and ϵ are equivalent, resulting in the dimensionless added bending rigidity being equal to the dimensionless added linear density. If $f > 1$, τ would have to be greater than ϵ to make the effect of added bending rigidity equal to that of increased linear density, it means the width, thickness and Young's modulus ratio values are more significant in increasing bending rigidity than linear density. To the contrary, if $f < 1$, it means these parameters tend to make the linear density increase more than bending rigidity.

Here we studied how width ratio parameter β affects the value of f . By taking the derivative of f to β , here we get

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial \beta} = -\frac{3\epsilon \zeta (\zeta + 1)^2}{(\beta \epsilon \zeta + 1)^2} \quad (19)$$

For any cantilever resonator and adsorbate, the variables such as β , ϵ , and ζ in formula f are always larger than 0. Thus $\frac{\partial f}{\partial \beta}$ will be less than 0, and f will decrease with the increment of width ratio β . It means when β is 0, f will be the maximum value. The minimum value of f is achieved when β reaches its maximum value, as β represents the relative width of the adsorbate compared to the cantilever resonator, and its maximum value is 1.

Then the partial derivative of f to ϵ is calculated as follows

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial \epsilon} = -\frac{3\beta \zeta (\zeta + 1)^2}{(\beta \epsilon \zeta + 1)^2} \quad (20)$$

Similar to $\frac{\partial f}{\partial \beta}$, $\frac{\partial f}{\partial \epsilon}$ is always less than 0 when the ϵ is greater than 0. The range of ϵ is decided by the Young's modulus ratio between the adsorbate and cantilever. In typical cases, resonators are typically constructed using silicon, while the materials of the adsorbate could be across a wide range of substances found in nature. When $\epsilon = 0$, the value of f reaches its maximum, and as ϵ increases, f gradually decreases.

Then we show the derivative of f to ζ as follows,

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial \zeta} = \frac{2\beta^2 \epsilon^2 \zeta^3 + 7\beta \epsilon \zeta^2 - 3\beta \epsilon + 8\zeta + 6}{(\beta \epsilon \zeta + 1)^2} \quad (21)$$

The minimum value of f related to β , ϵ , and ζ can be found by solving $\frac{\partial f}{\partial \zeta}(\epsilon) = 0$. And the solution of ϵ is as follows

$$\epsilon_v = \begin{cases} \frac{\sqrt{3}(1 + \zeta) \sqrt{-5\zeta^2 - 6\zeta + 3} - 7\zeta^2 + 3}{4\beta \zeta^3}, & \epsilon \geq \epsilon_k \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}(1 + \zeta) \sqrt{-5\zeta^2 - 6\zeta + 3} + 7\zeta^2 - 3}{4\beta \zeta^3}, & \epsilon_{v,\min} < \epsilon < \epsilon_k \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

where ϵ_v is the curve corresponding to the minimum value of f , ϵ_k is the critical point of ϵ_v , and $\epsilon_{v,\min}$ is the minimum value of ϵ_v . The value of ϵ_k is as follows

$$\epsilon_k = \frac{5\sqrt{6} + 15}{3\beta}$$

The corresponding maximum value of ζ along curve ϵ_v is ζ_k , here

$$\zeta_k = \frac{2\sqrt{6} - 3}{5}$$

It means the minimum f only exist when $\zeta \leq \frac{2\sqrt{6}-3}{5}$. $\epsilon_{v,\min}$ is the value of ϵ_v when ζ tends to 0,

$$\epsilon_{v,\min} = \lim_{\zeta \rightarrow 0} \epsilon_v = \frac{2}{\beta}$$

Moreover, it is crucial to determine the function ϵ_s for which makes $f = 1$. This condition indicates that the parameters along the curve have an equal impact on augmenting both the added area and moment of inertia of the cross-section. Consequently, this leads to a comparable trend of increasing bending rigidity and linear density. ϵ_s is presented as follows

$$\epsilon_s = -\frac{4\zeta + 2}{\beta \zeta (\zeta - 1)} \quad (23)$$

If $\epsilon > \epsilon_s$, the value of f will be smaller than 1. Conversely, when $\epsilon < \epsilon_s$, f will be greater than 1.

Fig. 2 illustrates the curves of ϵ_v and ϵ_s , as well as the curved surface of f . For any ϵ and ζ that are above the curve of ϵ_s , f will be always greater than 1, which means the added area will be more than the added moment of inertia, and the cross-section of the cantilever is more likely to be more inertial. On the opposite, if their values blow the curve of ϵ_s , added moment of inertia will take the major role that makes the cross-section stiffer.

As depicted in Fig. 2, it can be observed that f remains consistently greater than 1 for any $\zeta \geq 1$, irrespective of the specific values assigned to ϵ and β . The analysis reveals that the added moment of inertia

Fig. 2. The function f , which represents the ratio of the dimensionless added moment of inertia to the added area, is plotted as a curved surface. The curve ε_s corresponds to $f = 1$, while the piecewise function ε_v represents the minimum value of f with the changes of β and ε . The breakpoints for ε_v are denoted as (ζ_k, ε_k) . (ζ_j, ε_j) represents the maximum value of $\beta \cdot \varepsilon$ that guarantees the added bending rigidity surpasses the added linear density of the cross-section. $\varepsilon_{v,\min}$ signifies the minimum value of ε_v that guarantees a monotonic increase of f as ζ decreases.

consistently exceeds the added area, indicating a greater propensity for the cross-section to augment its bending rigidity rather than its linear density. The cantilever will be more sensitive for the measurement of bending stiffness of adsorbates. What is more, for the condition that ζ is close to 0 or 1, $\varepsilon \cdot \beta$ could change significantly and still below the ε_s curve. This result reveals that for the cantilever resonator with a cubic adsorbate when ζ is close to 0 or exceeds 1, the cross-section tends to have a more significant increase of additional bending rigidity compared to the linear density.

As shown in Fig. 2, there is an intersection between curves ε_v and ε_k . The intersection point (ζ_j, ε_j) corresponds to the minimum value of the curve ε_s . ε_j is the maximum value of ε for which the effect of added moment of inertia is always greater than that of the added area of the cross-section. Indeed, if $\varepsilon < \varepsilon_j$, it implies that for the added bending rigidity to equal the added linear density, τ must always be greater than ε . This suggests that the bending rigidity of the section is more likely to increase than its linear density. As (ζ_j, ε_j) is the intersection of ε_s and ε_v , the values of ζ_j and ε_j could be calculated by building the following equation

$$\varepsilon_s - \varepsilon_v = -\frac{(\zeta + 1)\left[\sqrt{3}(\zeta - 1)\sqrt{-5\zeta^2 - 6\zeta + 3} + 9\zeta^2 + 6\zeta - 3\right]}{4\beta\zeta^3(\zeta - 1)} = 0. \quad (24)$$

By solving the equation, ζ_j and ε_j are calculated as follows

$$(\zeta_j, \varepsilon_j) = \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}-1}{2}, \frac{4\sqrt{3}+8}{\beta}\right).$$

The minimum value of ε_v is achieved when the thickness ratio ζ is approximately equal to $\frac{\sqrt{3}-1}{2}$. This implies that making the thickness ratio ζ close to $\frac{\sqrt{3}-1}{2}$ will render the cantilever more suitable for measuring the added linear density. In this circumstance, the value of $\varepsilon \cdot \beta$ is tended to make $f < 1$. To measure the mass of the adsorbate, the value of ε , β , and ζ would be better located along the ε_v curve, as they correspond to the minimum f . If ε is less than $\frac{4\sqrt{3}+8}{\beta}$, the value of f will always be greater than 1. Thus, for $\tau/\varepsilon = 1$, the effect of added bending rigidity will be greater than the added linear density of the cross-section.

Due to $0 < \beta \leq 1$, the minimum value of ε_v for any β and ζ could be calculated as $\varepsilon_{v,\min} = 2$. If $\varepsilon \leq 2$, the minimum value of f will be 3, thus τ/ε must be greater than 3 to make added linear density more significant than added bending rigidity. In this scenario, the positive influence of the added bending rigidity of the cross-section is more than three times greater than the negative impact of the added linear density. f related to specific ε values are shown in Fig. 3(a). For any β , the minimum ε for f always greater than 1 is $\varepsilon = 4\sqrt{3} + 8$ and the corresponding f value is shown in Fig. 3(b).

We have proved that f decreases with the increment of β and ε , by setting β and ε as their minimum values of 0. The maximum value of f for specific ζ value is given as

$$f_{\max} = 4\zeta^2 + 6\zeta + 3. \quad (25)$$

The minimum value of f is determined by the value of ε . Specifically, when $0 \leq \varepsilon \leq 2/\beta$, the minimum value of f is $f_{\min} = 3$. This implies that in order for the effect of added linear density of the cross-section to surpass that of the added bending rigidity, the value of λ must be more than three times that of ε . When $\varepsilon > 2/\beta$, f_{\min} will be influenced by the values of ε , β , and ζ . By substituting Eq. (22) into Eq. (18), f_{\min} can be shown as follows

$$f_{\min} = \begin{cases} 3, & 0 < \varepsilon \leq \frac{2}{\beta} \\ \frac{\zeta_v^2 \left(9\zeta_v + \sqrt{3}\sqrt{-5\zeta_v^2 - 6\zeta_v + 3} + 15 \right)}{\sqrt{3}\sqrt{-5\zeta_v^2 - 6\zeta_v + 3} - 3\zeta_v + 3}, & \frac{2}{\beta} < \varepsilon \leq \frac{5\sqrt{6} + 15}{3\beta} \\ \frac{\zeta_v^2 \left(9\zeta_v - \sqrt{3}\sqrt{-5\zeta_v^2 - 6\zeta_v + 3} + 15 \right)}{\sqrt{3}\sqrt{-5\zeta_v^2 - 6\zeta_v + 3} + 3\zeta_v - 3}, & \varepsilon > \frac{5\sqrt{6} + 15}{3\beta} \end{cases}, \quad (26)$$

where ζ_v represents the ζ value along the curve ε_v . It is obtained by solving Eq. (22) with the values of $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_v$ and $\beta = 1$.

The ratio of added bending rigidity to added linear density of the cross-section could be deduced by substituting Eq. (18) into Eq. (16). It is presented as follows

Fig. 3. For any given values of β and ζ , the maximum and minimum values of f for a specific value of ϵ . (a) To ensure that the function f consistently increases with an increment of ζ , the maximum value of ϵ is 2. (b) To ensure that f remains above 1, regardless of the values of β and ζ , the maximum allowable value for ϵ is $4\sqrt{3} + 8$.

$$\frac{\eta}{\lambda} = \frac{\epsilon}{\tau} \cdot f. \quad (27)$$

2.3. Exploring the influence of adsorbate length and location on cantilever sensitivity

The subsequent investigation is the positioning and length of the adsorbate impact on the cantilever resonator for the first five bending modes. Furthermore, the difference in the impact is studied between the added stiffness and added mass for the same adsorbate location and length.

As shown in Fig. 4(a), for the first five bending modes, $g_{n,E}$ increases as α increases despite the location of the adsorbate. For the same α value, where the adsorbate is located on the cantilever with more bending, $g_{n,E}$ will be greater. For $\alpha = 1$, $g_{n,E}$ will be the same maximum value as 1 for all the first five bending modes.

Similarly, in Fig. 4(b), it can be observed that for the first five bending modes, $g_{n,M}$ increases with α increasing, regardless of the adsorbate location. When the adsorbate is positioned at a location with a higher vibration amplitude of the cantilever, the corresponding $g_{n,M}$ value will be higher for a given α . Specifically, when $\alpha = 1$, $g_{n,M}$ reaches its maximum value of 1 for all the first five bending modes.

The curves of $g_{n,E}$ and $g_{n,M}$ in Fig. 4(a) and (b), respectively, exhibit notable symmetry with respect to the centre of the beam length direction for all different orders of the natural frequencies. In order to quantitatively assess the symmetry between the $g_{n,E}$ and $g_{n,M}$ curves for the first five natural frequencies, we have developed the mathematical model as follows

$$g_{n,E}(\chi_m) = g_{n,M}(1 - \chi_m) \pm \Delta g_n, \quad (28)$$

where Δg_n is the random variable and $\Delta g_n \sim N(\mu_n, \sigma_n^2)$. σ_n is the standard deviation following 3 σ rule, the probability is 99.73% for

$$g_{n,E} \in [g_{n,M}(1 - \chi_m) - 3\sigma_n, g_{n,M}(1 - \chi_m) + 3\sigma_n]. \quad (29)$$

The data in Table 2 show that the values of σ are less than 10^{-5} for the first five bending natural frequencies of the cantilever resonator. This indicates that the mass and bending stiffness of the adsorbate have equal opposite effects on these bending modes of the cantilever.

By establishing the relationship between the ratio of $g_{n,E}$ to $g_{n,M}$, we can determine the relative contribution of the added stiffness and added mass to the bending modes of the cantilever. The corresponding expression is presented as

$$\frac{g_{n,E}}{g_{n,M}} = \frac{\int_{\chi_s}^{\chi_c} \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2} \right)^2 d\chi}{\int_{\chi_s}^{\chi_c} U_n^2(\chi) d\chi} \cdot \frac{\int_0^1 U_n^2(\chi) d\chi}{\int_0^1 \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2} \right)^2 d\chi}, \quad (30)$$

and the curves for the first five bending modes are shown in Fig. 5.

Table 2

The average and standard deviation of Δg_n for the first five bending modes.

Parameter	μ_n	σ_n
1st bending mode	5.03×10^{-16}	8.03×10^{-16}
2nd bending mode	6.46×10^{-15}	5.14×10^{-14}
3rd bending mode	-3.51×10^{-13}	1.31×10^{-11}
4th bending mode	1.29×10^{-9}	5.31×10^{-9}
5th bending mode	4.09×10^{-8}	1.57×10^{-6}

Function $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ quantifies the relative sensitivity of the cantilever to added stiffness and mass when $\eta = \lambda = 1$, which varies with the changes in the location and length of the adsorbate. For $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ greater than 1, the cantilever is more sensitive to the bending stiffness of the adsorbate. On the opposite, if $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ is smaller than 1, the mass of the adsorbate will take the main role and drops the natural frequencies of the cantilever.

The greater the value of $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ is, the more sensitive the cantilever is to the bending stiffness of the adsorbate. According to the illustration shown in Fig. 5, it can be observed that the ratio of $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ reaches its maximum value when the adsorbate is located at the fixed end of the cantilever resonator. Conversely, the minimum value of $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ is attained when the adsorbate is positioned at the free end of the cantilever. This conclusion holds true for the first five bending modes. In addition, as the order of the bending mode increases, the maximum value of $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ decreases. Thus, the fixed end of the first bending mode exhibits the highest sensitivity to bending stiffness. On the contrary, when the adsorbate is located at the free end, the lower order of natural frequency results in a smaller minimum value of $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$. This denotes that the free end of the cantilever of the first-order bending mode will be the most sensitive to mass.

Furthermore, for the bending modes, when the adsorbate centre is located in the middle in the length direction of the cantilever, no matter how long the adsorbate is, $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ will be 1 all the time. The sensitivity of the middle of the cantilever to the mass and stiffness measurement of the adsorbate will be identical. Furthermore, the sensitivity of the cantilever increases as the length of the adsorbate decreases. To improve the accuracy and stability of the measurements, it is advisable to minimize the length of the adsorbate relative to the cantilever and position it near the fixed or free end of the cantilever resonator when measuring either stiffness or mass.

Since the cantilever resonator exhibits a pronounced sensitivity to the stiffness of the adsorbate when located at the fixed end, λ should be significantly greater than η to render the stiffness effect of the adsorbate negligible. Thus, for the adsorbate on the fixed end, the mass effect of the adsorbate can be ignored when measuring the stiffness. Conversely,

Fig. 4. The values of $g_{n,E}$ and $g_{n,M}$ for the first five bending modes of the cantilever resonator vary depending on the lengths and locations of the adsorbate. (a) $g_{n,E}$, (b) $g_{n,M}$.

when the adsorbate is situated at the free end of the cantilever, the mass effect of the adsorbate cannot be neglected in the measurement of stiffness. Additionally, as α increases, the value of $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ will be close to 1, indicating that the cantilever resonator is equally sensitive to both the mass and stiffness of the adsorbate.

2.4. Theoretical analysis of $g_{n,E}$, $g_{n,M}$, and their ratio

To study the theoretical maximum of the relative sensitivity of cantilever resonators, as well as determine the precision adsorbate location that makes the cantilever have the minimum or maximum sensitivity to added mass or stiffness. Here a further analysis model is built with $\eta = \lambda = 1$.

When the length of the adsorbate is significantly shorter than that of the cantilever resonator, Fig. 4(a) and (b) demonstrate that $g_{n,E}$ and $g_{n,M}$ will approach zero for certain locations on the cantilever resonator. Here we simulated the condition that $\alpha = 0.02$, which represents that adsorbate is obviously shorter than the cantilever. The corresponding $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ values are shown in Fig. 6. There are specific locations on the cantilever where the adsorbate has no effect on the natural frequency of the cantilever resonator, regardless of the ratio of η to λ . This implies that such locations are not suitable for identifying the adsorbate and should be avoided in practical applications. When the natural frequencies exceed the third-order bending mode, placing the adsorbate between two wave crests will lead to a decrease in sensitivity to both the added stiffness and added mass.

We developed the following formulas to describe the relationship between the maximum value of the square of cantilever displacements when α approaches 0. Additionally, we established a formula to determine the relationship between the maximum value of the square of the second derivative of $U_n(\chi)$ with respect to χ , denoted as $\left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2$.

The formulas are derived from Eq. (15) and presented as follows

$$\begin{cases} J_{n,E} = \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} \frac{g_{n,E}}{\max(g_{n,E})} = \frac{\left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(\chi)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2}{\left(\frac{\partial^2 U_n(0)}{\partial \chi^2}\right)^2}, \\ J_{n,M} = \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} \frac{g_{n,M}}{\max(g_{n,M})} = \frac{U_n^2(\chi)}{U_n^2(1)} \end{cases}, \quad (31)$$

where $J_{n,E}$ and $J_{n,M}$ represent the theoretical maximum value of $g_{n,E}$ and $g_{n,M}$, and they are illustrated in Fig. 7. For χ values make $J_{n,E}$ or $J_{n,M}$ equal to 0, the cantilever will be insensitive to the added stiffness or added mass of the adsorbate. The values of χ are listed in Table 3. The values of χ_m that make the curves in Fig. 6 equal to 0 are corresponding to the values of χ that make $J_{n,E}$ and $J_{n,M}$ close to 0. As indicated in Table 3 and Fig. 6, the parameter χ influences both $J_{n,E}$ and $J_{n,M}$ to converge towards 0, but this effect is observed only for bending modes higher than the third order. Furthermore, although these values of χ tend to bring $J_{n,E}$ and $J_{n,M}$ closer to 0, it should be noted that the values are not exactly identical. Hence, for the values of χ that are not ideal for measuring both the added stiffness and the added mass, a suitable compromise can be achieved by selecting the midpoint value.

As depicted in Table 3 and Fig. 7, added stiffness to the fixed end of the cantilever has a greater impact than added mass, while the free end exhibits an opposite trend. These findings are consistent with the curves shown in Fig. 5. For bending modes above the third order, $J_{n,E}$ and $J_{n,M}$ are identical except for the wave crests nearest to the fixed and free ends of the cantilever, resulting in equivalent sensitivity to added mass and added stiffness of the cantilever. Moreover, when the adsorbate is situated in the trough between two neighbouring wave crests, the value of χ_m that makes both the stiffness and mass effects approach zero will be similar, as demonstrated in Fig. 7(c–e). In this scenario, the

Fig. 5. The ratio of added stiffness to the added mass of the cantilever for adsorbate with different lengths and located at various locations on the cantilever when η equals λ . (a) 1st bending mode. (b) 2nd bending mode. (c) 3rd bending mode. (d) 4th bending mode. (e) 5th bending mode.

Table 3

The locations of the adsorbate on the cantilever that is not sensitive to added stiffness, added mass, or both for the first five bending modes.

Bending mode	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th
Stiffness	1	0.217	0.132	0.094	0.074
		1	0.497	0.356	0.277
			1	0.642	0.500
				1	0.721
					1
Mass	0	0	0	0	0
		0.783	0.504	0.358	0.279
			0.868	0.644	0.500
				0.906	0.723
					0.927
Both			0.5	0.357	0.278
				0.643	0.500
					0.500
					0.722

cantilever will become insensitive to both the added mass and added stiffness of the adsorbate. This renders the cantilever unsuitable for measuring the properties of the adsorbate.

We created the following equation to investigate the extreme relative sensitivity of cantilever resonators to added stiffness and added mass caused by the adsorbate.

$$J_n = \frac{J_{n,E}}{J_{n,M}}, \quad (32)$$

where J_n is the theoretical maximum relative sensitivity of added stiffness to added mass that $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ or $G_n(\eta = \lambda)$ could be realized, while J_n^{-1} corresponds to the maximum relative sensitivity of added mass to added stiffness. J_n curves of the first five bending modes are displayed in Fig. 8.

These results explained that the fixed end of the cantilever exhibits the maximum value of $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$, while the free end displays the minimum value, as depicted in Fig. 5. Furthermore, the sudden change observed in the curves of Fig. 5(c-e) for small α correspond to abrupt variations in Fig. 8 for bending modes beyond the third order. This behaviour stems from the similarity of χ values that yield $J_{n,E}$ and $J_{n,M}$ approaching 0, resulting in abrupt transitions of J_n values from small to exceedingly large magnitudes.

As depicted in Fig. 8, it can be observed that for the purpose of determining the mass of the adsorbate and eliminating the stiffness effect,

Fig. 6. The ratio of added stiffness to the added mass of the adsorbate is calculated for the first five bending modes when the adsorbate length is much shorter than the cantilever. The behaviour depicted by the curves is dependent on the ratio of the added bending rigidity to the added linear density with a constant length ratio of $\alpha = 0.02$ between the adsorbate and the cantilever. The range of the ratio η/λ spans from 0 to infinity.

Fig. 7. The curves of $J_{n,E}$ and $J_{n,M}$ depict the maximum sensitivity of the cantilever's location to the added stiffness and added mass of adsorbate for the first five bending modes. (a) 1st bending mode. (b) 2nd bending mode. (c) 3rd bending mode. (d) 4th bending mode. (e) 5th bending mode.

Fig. 8. J_n curves indicate the potential range of $g_{n,E}/g_{n,M}$ values, with J_n representing the maximum added stiffness to added mass ratio when $J_n > 1$, and J_n^{-1} representing the maximum added mass to added stiffness sensitivity when $J_n < 1$. These curves provide insight into whether the stiffness or mass of an adsorbate has a greater impact on the cantilever's first five bending modes.

selecting the free end of the cantilever proves to be the most optimal choice. For the second-order bending mode, positioning the adsorbate at $\chi_m = 0.217$ from the free end of the cantilever, $\chi_m = 0.132$ for the third bending mode, $\chi_m = 0.0942$ for the fourth bending mode, and $\chi_m = 0.074$ for the fifth bending mode can provide desirable sensitivity to the mass effect while minimizing the influence of stiffness effects. On the other hand, to optimize the measurement of the stiffness of the adsorbate and eliminate the mass effect, positioning the adsorbate at the fixed end of the cantilever would be the best choice. Moreover, for the second bending mode, placing the adsorbate at $\chi_m = 0.783$ of the cantilever, $\chi_m = 0.868$ for the third bending mode, $\chi_m = 0.906$ for the fourth bending mode, and $\chi_m = 0.927$ for the fifth bending mode can provide ideal sensitivity to the stiffness effect while eliminating the undesired mass effects.

3. Results

Materials of adsorbates exhibiting significant differences in Young's modulus and density are studied. The mathematical model of the cross-section is validated through the implementation of FEA. Additionally, the FEA method and experimental results are employed and verify the mathematical model of relative sensitivity G_n .

3.1. Analysis of different materials

This section analyses the prevalent adsorbate materials utilized in nano/micro-mechanical resonators, aiming to determine the range of the ratio between the added bending rigidity and the added linear density of the cross-section.

Here we studied the materials widely applied in biomaterial research, such as breast epithelial cancer cells (MCF-7) [25,63], myosin [3], tobacco mosaic virus (TMV) [30], and Escherichia coli bacteria (E-coli) [18]. As well as the materials that have been applied in previous studies for theoretic validation, such as polymer [6], gold [18,64], and platinum [5,65]. Furthermore, diamond material is considered for studying the condition that adsorbates are apparently stiffer than the resonator [66,67]. The Young's modulus and density of these materials are presented in Table 4.

Pure silicon is a highly popular material for nano-mechanical resonators due to its exceptional chemical stability and the capability to achieve nanoscale precision during fabrication [68]. The Young's modulus and density of silicon cantilevers are 168 GPa and 2.329 g/cm^3 [6]. The height ratio between the adsorbate and resonator is limited to $\zeta \leq$

Table 4

The Young's modulus and density of adsorbate with different materials.

Material	Young's modulus (GPa)	Density (g/cm^3)
MCF-7	0.001 (approx.)	1 (approx.)
Myosin	0.7	0.183
TMV	6(axial)	0.88
E-coli	1	0.9
Polymer	1.36	0.746
Gold	79	19.3
Platinum	168	21.44
Diamond	1140	3.51

Table 5

The range of ratios of added bending rigidity to added linear density of various adsorbate materials on a silicon cantilever.

Material	ϵ	τ	ϵ/τ	Range of η/λ
MCF-7	5.95×10^{-6}	4.29×10^{-1}	1.39×10^{-5}	$(4.16 \times 10^{-5}, 4.30 \times 10^{-4})$
Myosin	4.17×10^{-3}	7.86×10^{-2}	5.30×10^{-2}	$(1.59 \times 10^{-1}, 1.64)$
TMV	3.57×10^{-2}	3.78×10^{-1}	9.45×10^{-2}	$(2.84 \times 10^{-1}, 2.93)$
E-coli	5.95×10^{-3}	3.86×10^{-1}	1.54×10^{-2}	$(4.62 \times 10^{-2}, 4.78 \times 10^{-1})$
Polymer	8.10×10^{-3}	3.20×10^{-1}	2.53×10^{-2}	$(7.58 \times 10^{-2}, 7.83 \times 10^{-1})$
Gold	4.70×10^{-1}	8.29	5.67×10^{-2}	$(1.70 \times 10^{-1}, 1.76)$
Platinum	1.00	9.21	1.09×10^{-1}	$(3.26 \times 10^{-1}, 3.37)$
Diamond	6.79	1.51	4.50	$(7.83, 1.40 \times 10^2)$

2. ϵ and τ are related to the properties of the adsorbate and cantilever, while f_{\min} and f_{\max} have been calculated, the range of dimensionless added bending stiffness to added linear density ratio of the cross-section can be calculated by applying Eq. (27).

Considering silicon's characteristic as a rigid material, the Young's modulus ratio (ϵ) between most of the listed materials and silicon is generally less than 2, with the exception of diamond. Based on Eqs. (25) and (26), the range of f will be ($3 < f < 31$), While f_{\min} for diamond could be calculated as $f_{\min} = 1.74$ by using Eq. (26). The ranges of η/λ of the cross-section of different material adsorbates located on the silicon cantilever are shown in Table 5.

The materials, except diamond, are always with $\epsilon/\tau < 1$, which is because the ratios of the Young's modulus to the density of these materials are smaller than silicon. As we have learned that the geometry parameters of the cross-section have the trend to increase the bending rigidity more than linear density, so with some materials with $\epsilon/\tau < 1$ it will be possible to make the effect of bending rigidity higher than the linear density of the cross-section, such as myosin, TMV, gold, and platinum in Table 5. It should be noted that the η/λ values of the

materials in Table 5 are not always less than 1. This implies that the bending rigidity of the cross-section should not be disregarded, except in cases that ε/τ is significantly less than 1, such as MCF-7. Moreover, if the ε/τ of the material, such as diamond or carbon nanotube [69], is much greater than 1, the linear density of the adsorbate will be relatively insignificant.

The natural frequencies of the cantilever resonator are subject to the influence of multiple factors, including the location and length of the adsorbate, as well as the added bending rigidity and linear density of the cross-section. These parameters collectively contribute to the overall behaviour and characteristics of the resonator's natural frequency response. The magnitude of G_n serves as a useful indicator to discern the relative impact of the adsorbate's bending stiffness and mass on the natural frequency of the resonator. It aids in determining which factor exerts a more prominent influence on the overall behaviour and characteristics of the resonator's natural frequency.

3.2. FEA simulation for mathematical model validation

To verify the accuracy of our mathematical model in estimating the ratio of added bending rigidity to added linear density of the cross-section for adsorbates made of various materials combined with a silicon cantilever, we conducted the following simulations. Moreover, we validated the mathematical model for G_n by comparing its results with those obtained through the FEA method.

The relative differences between FEA and mathematical model could be calculated by using

$$\Delta G_n = \frac{G_{n,\text{Math}} - G_{n,\text{FEA}}}{G_{n,\text{Math}}} \times 100\%, \quad (33)$$

where $G_{n,\text{Math}}$ and $G_{n,\text{FEA}}$ represent the G_n calculated by using mathematical and FEA method, ΔG_n is the relative difference.

If the length of adsorbate is the same as that of the cantilever resonator, the length ratio α will be 1, G_n in Eq. (14) will be presented as follows

$$G_n(\alpha = 1) = \frac{\eta}{\lambda}. \quad (34)$$

In this particular scenario, the values of G_n for the first five bending modes will be equal, regardless of the order of the natural frequency. This means if we set the adsorbate fully cover the surface of the cantilever resonator in the length direction, the FEA model could be used to validate the mathematical model of the ratio of added bending rigidity to added linear density of the cross-section.

The FEA method was applied to validate the mathematical model. The length, width, and thickness of the resonator are 60 μm , 17 μm , and 0.5 μm , respectively [70]. The length, width, and thickness ratio between the adsorbate and cantilever are set as 1, 1/2, and 1, respectively. The cantilever is set as pure silicon with the Young's modulus and density are 168 GPa and 2.329 g/cm^3 , and the adsorbate is set as the materials listed in Table 4. Eq. (34) is used to calculate η/λ of different materials by using the mathematical and FEA method, which is based on the first bending mode of the cantilever. Table 6 presents the η/λ of different adsorbate materials calculated by using mathematical and FEA methods, along with the relative difference.

The maximum error between the mathematical model and the FEA result is 14.761%, indicating a good agreement between the two methods. Therefore, the mathematical model can effectively calculate the ratio of added bending rigidity to the linear density of the cross-section.

To validate the mathematical model of G_n , we set the length, width, and thickness ratio between the adsorbate and cantilever resonator in the simulation as 0.25, 0.5, and 1, respectively. Polymer is used as the material of adsorbate to validate the mathematical method. According to Table 5, the Young's modulus ratio between the polymer adsorbate and silicon cantilever is 8.10×10^{-3} , while the density ratio is 3.20×10^{-1} . The adsorbate was positioned from the fixed end to the free end of the cantilever, and the relative location of the adsorbate

Table 6

η/λ of different adsorbate materials and silicon cantilever calculated using mathematical and FEA methods.

Material	Mathematical	FEA	Difference
MCF-7	1.803×10^{-4}	1.965×10^{-4}	-9.007%
Myosin	6.884×10^{-1}	6.689×10^{-1}	2.829%
TMV	1.208	1.168	3.291%
E-coli	1.998×10^{-1}	1.941×10^{-2}	2.886%
Polymer	3.278×10^{-1}	3.180×10^{-1}	3.007%
Gold	6.076×10^{-1}	5.604×10^{-1}	7.771%
Platinum	9.772×10^{-1}	8.779×10^{-1}	10.159%
Diamond	1.677×10^1	1.430×10^1	14.761%

Fig. 9. The values of G_n for the first five bending modes were determined through simulations of a polymer adsorbate on a silicon cantilever using both mathematical and FEA methods. The results obtained from the mathematical method are depicted by lines, while the FEA simulations are represented by dots.

centre to cantilever χ_m are 1/8, 1/4, 1/2, 3/4, and 7/8, respectively. Fig. 9 illustrated the G_n calculated with the theoretical method and the value produced by using the FEA method.

Fig. 9 exhibited that the first bending mode has the greatest G_n value compared with higher modes. The fixed end of the cantilever exhibits the highest relative sensitivity of added stiffness to added mass. On the other hand, the free end of the cantilever exhibits the highest relative sensitivity of added mass to added stiffness. The value of G_n for the adsorbate positioned at the centre of the cantilever corresponds to the η/λ values presented in Table 6. The results align well with Eq. (14). The mathematical and FEA results depicted in Fig. 9 are in good agreement with each other for the first five bending modes of the mechanical resonator. The detailed FEA model, data, and the grid-independent study [71] are carried out and presented in Appendix B.

Moreover, according to the results, positioning the adsorbate towards the free end of the cantilever can enhance the mass sensitivity and potentially eliminate any unwanted stiffness-related effects. This study explains why previous studies on determining mass typically involved coating adsorbates with a small thickness ratio and positioning them close to the free end of the cantilever [5,22].

3.3. Experiment validation

Here we used experimental results to validate the mathematical model in effecting the measurement accuracy and stability of the adsorbate's Young's modulus and density. Here, Belardinelli's experiment results are used and verify the mathematical model [6].

There was a polymeric block coated near the fixed-end of a cantilever resonator. The parameters of the cantilever resonator and adsorbate are shown in Table 7.

Table 7

The parameters of the adsorbate and cantilever.

Parameters	Length	Width	Thickness	Young's modulus	Density
Adsorbate	45.79 μm	45.20 μm	3.28 μm	1.36 GPa	0.746 g/cm^3
Cantilever	455.21 μm	47.13 μm	2 μm	168 GPa	2.329 g/cm^3

Table 8

The identified values of Young's modulus and density of the added polymer with different combinations of flexural modes in Belardinelli's experiment.

Combination of modes	Young's modulus (GPa)	Density (g/cm^3)
1st flex.mode + 2nd flex.mode	1.44	-65.77
1st flex.mode + 3rd flex.mode	1.40	-0.96
1st flex.mode + 4nd flex.mode	1.39	-1.62
1st flex.mode + 5nd flex.mode	1.36	0.74

Belardinelli used the combination of the first bending mode with higher bending mode to measure the Young's modulus and density of the adsorbate, and the results are shown in Table 8.

Based on the parameters, the utilization of Eq. (14) yields the corresponding values of G_n , as $G_1 = 5.25 \times 10^3$, $G_2 = 1.05 \times 10^2$, $G_3 = 1.06 \times 10^1$, $G_4 = 2.32$, and $G_5 = 8.99 \times 10^{-1}$, respectively. As the order of the bending modes increases, the values of G_n diminish, indicating a reduction in the ratio of stiffness to mass sensitivity of the cantilever. It is noteworthy that the first bending mode demonstrates the highest value of G_n . When employing the first bending mode, regardless of its combination with other modes, the estimation of Young's modulus should exhibit significant accuracy and stability compared to the density estimation. This observation is clearly evident in Table 8. Moreover, as the order of natural frequencies increase, the values of G_n decline, indicating an enhanced sensitivity of the cantilever to the variations of density of the adsorbate. This observation is consistent with the density measurement results, which have a trend of improvements in accuracy. Specifically, for the fifth bending mode that $G_5 < 1$, the cantilever demonstrates the highest sensitivity to the density variation, and the density result is obviously more accurate than lower order as shown in Table 8.

4. Discussion

A dimensionless mathematical model has been built by employing the Rayleigh–Ritz method. It can quantify the relative sensitivity of the added stiffness to added mass effects arising from adsorbate on a cantilever resonator. By partitioning the primary investigation into two independent sub-problems, namely the cross-section property problem and the influence of adsorbate position and length problem, a comprehensive study of the coupled parameters is achieved for the first five bending modes. By using this method, the dimensionality of the problem is reduced, this approach facilitates an exploration of the intricate relationship between the variables, instead of fixing the values of other parameters to study a specific parameter, as done in previous studies [47].

As for the cross-section property, the results demonstrate that the added bending rigidity of the cross-section tends to exhibit a more pronounced increase compared to the added linear density when the Young's modulus ratio between the adsorbate and cantilever was less than $4\sqrt{3} + 8$. Furthermore, this difference will be further magnified by the increment of thickness ratio and the decrease of the Young's modulus and width ratios. Commonly, for the Young's modulus and density ratio between the adsorbate and cantilever are typically at the same magnitude, the bending rigidity of the cross-section will exceed the linear density. However, for materials with a significantly higher Young's modulus ratio compared to the density ratio, such as MCF-7, the bending rigidity effect of the cross-section will be negligible.

Regarding the influence of the adsorbate's location and length on the cantilever for the first five bending modes, the added bending rigidity and added linear density ratios of the cross-section are set equal

to eliminate the cross-section property effect. The results revealed that the added mass and added stiffness had perfectly symmetrical effects on the cantilever. The symmetrical axis is the centre of the cantilever in the length direction. It indicates that the adsorbate located at the fixed end of the cantilever exhibits the highest relative sensitivity of added stiffness to added mass, while the free end shows the most added mass to added stiffness sensitivity for the first five bending modes. Besides, lower bending modes exhibit better relative sensitivity, resulting in more stable outcomes in practical applications. Conversely, increasing the adsorbate length or positioning it near the centre along the length dimension led to an equal sensitivity of the cantilever resonator to both the added mass and added stiffness of the adsorbate.

The FEA and experiment results demonstrate the effectiveness of our proposed model in assessing the impact of the adsorbate's stiffness and mass on the cantilever. Additionally, the results indicate that the mathematical model is applicable in evaluating nano-mechanical resonators and determining whether the adsorbate's stiffness or mass can be disregarded in practical situations. This enables the reduction of undesired parameters to the lowest possible level, ultimately enhancing the accuracy and reliability of real-world applications.

To measure the stiffness or Young's modulus of an adsorbate, it is preferable to position it near the fixed end of the cantilever and utilize the first bending mode. When adsorbates are randomly placed on the cantilever, the most accurate measurement can be determined by identifying the maximum value of G_n for the adsorbate's location and bending mode order. Conversely, the location and order of adsorbates that minimize the value of G_n will yield the most precise measurement of the adsorbate's mass or density.

The engineering significance of this study is to reveal the stiffness and mass influence of adsorbate on cantilever resonators. This could help discover the reason why using a higher bending mode could help improve the measurement of relative properties related to the mass and stiffness of adsorbate. It could be used to determine the best location of adsorbates for the measurement of the density or Young's modulus of cells, bacteria, viruses, and proteins. Improve the mass spectrometry or Young's modulus density measurement accuracy and stability.

Since the theory assumes that the mode shape of the cantilever remains unchanged when an adsorbate is present on it, there is a potential increase in error when dealing with larger, heavier, or stiffer adsorbates compared to the cantilever resonators [18]. With considering the effect of mode shape changes, the accuracy and stability of this study could be further improved [22]. Additionally, the study is based on a dimensionless model approach, which theoretically allows for its application across various scales, as long as the adsorbate and cantilever retain their physical and mechanical properties without any significant special mechanical effects at the nano or macro scale. This implies that the study should be applicable to cantilever resonators ranging from hundreds of nanometers [20] to hundreds of micrometers [6,29] in size.

In summary, our study uncovers the intricate interplay between the added stiffness and added mass effects attributed to the adsorbate on the cantilever resonator. The proposed model resolves the problem of determining whether the mass or stiffness of the adsorbate can be disregarded in micro/nano-mechanical resonators. By leveraging this mathematical model, researchers can assess whether the mass or stiffness of the adsorbate can be disregarded in real-world experiments, as well as determine optimal locations for adsorbate placement to enhance the sensitivity for mass or stiffness measurement. By reducing the dimensionality of the problem, this approach facilitates an exploration of the intricate relationship between the variables, instead of fixing the values of other parameters to study a specific parameter, as done in previous studies [47]. This reduction in dimensionality allows for a more targeted and nuanced exploration of the specific variables involved, leading to a deeper understanding of their intricate relationships and their impact on the overall behaviour of the resonator system.

Fig. B.1. The FEA models are built by using Abaqus software. The cantilever's length, width, and thickness are 60 μm , 17 μm , and 0.5 μm , respectively. The material of the cantilever is silicon and the Young's modulus and density are 168 GPa and 2.329 g/cm^3 . The fixed end surface of the cantilever is constrained to prevent any displacement in any direction. (a) The bare cantilever. (b) The length, width, and thickness of the adsorbate are 60 μm , 8.5 μm , and 0.5 μm , respectively. The interface between the adsorbate and the resonator is constrained with a Tie type. (c) The polymer adsorbate located from the fixed end to the free end of the cantilever resonator. The length, width, and thickness of the cube are 15 μm , 8.5 μm , and 0.5 μm , respectively. The cube interface is constrained with a Tie type to the resonator.

5. Conclusions

To conclude, we have built a dimensionless mathematical model by employing the Rayleigh–Ritz method to quantify the relative sensitivity of the added stiffness to added mass effects arising from adsorbate on a cantilever resonator. The model agrees well with the FEA and experiment results.

Separating the primary investigation into two independent sub-problems enables a comprehensive study of the coupled parameters for the first five bending modes. The results demonstrate that the added bending rigidity of the cross-section tends to exhibit a more pronounced increase compared to the added linear density. The adsorbate located at the fixed end of the cantilever exhibits the highest relative sensitivity of added stiffness to the added mass. In contrast, the free end shows the most added mass to the added stiffness sensitivity for the first five bending modes. Besides, increasing the adsorbate length or positioning it near the centre along the length dimension decreases the relative sensitivity of the cantilever resonator.

This dimensionless method can be utilized to determine whether the effect of stiffness or mass can be disregarded in practical applications, aiding in identifying the optimal locations that minimize the influence of undesired parameters in micro or nanoscale cantilever resonators.

Overall, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of the complex relationships of the parameters between adsorbates and cantilevers, providing valuable insights for the design and optimization of cantilever resonator systems.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Yue Yang: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Yanling Tian:** Conceptualization, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Xianping Liu:** Validation, Supervision. **Yumeng Song:** Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. The rudimentary functions

A.1. The time-independent mode shape of the cantilever resonator

The time-independent mode shapes of the cantilever resonator, denoted as $\Phi_n(x)$, can be represented as follows.

$$\Phi_n(x) = C_n (\cos K_n x - \cosh K_n x) + (\sin K_n x - \sinh K_n x), \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where K_n is the modal wave-numbers of the cantilever, and it is determined by solving the equation $\cos(K_n L) \cosh(K_n L) = -1$. The values of $K_n L$ are 1.875, 4.694, 7.855, 10.996, and 14.137, respectively. The mode coefficients C_n fulfil

$$C_n = \frac{\cos K_n L + \cosh K_n L}{\sin K_n L - \sinh K_n L},$$

and $C_n = -1.362, -0.982, -1.001, -1.000, \text{ and } -1.000$, respectively [4].

Table B.1

The first five bending natural frequencies of the bare cantilever resonator by using the FEA method.

Order of bending	Natural frequency (Hz)
1st	1.89604×10^5
2nd	1.18790×10^6
3rd	3.32472×10^6
4th	6.51108×10^6
5th	1.07546×10^7

Based on Eq. (A.1), the dimensionless time-independent mode shape of the cantilever is given as

$$U_n(\chi) = C_n (\cos \kappa_n \chi - \cosh \kappa_n \chi) + (\sin \kappa_n \chi - \sinh \kappa_n \chi). \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The dimensionless modal wave number of the cantilever resonator κ_n is presented as $\kappa_n = K_n L$.

A.2. Bending rigidity $D_{R,C}$

The neutral surface location h_0 of the cross-section with adsorbate and cantilever can be calculated by using

$$E_C W_C \int_{h_0}^{h_0+T_C} z dz + E_R W_R \int_{h_0-T_R}^{h_0} z dz = 0. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

By solving Eq. (A.3), h_0 could be conducted as

$$h_0 = \frac{E_R W_R T_R^2 - E_C W_C T_C^2}{2(E_C W_C T_C + E_R W_R T_R)}. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The bending rigidity of the cross-section could be calculated by using

$$D_{R,C} = E_C I_{C h_0} + E_R I_{R h_0}, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where, $I_{C h_0}$ and $I_{R h_0}$ are the moments of inertia of the adsorbate and resonator to the neutral surface location h_0 . They are presented as

$$\begin{cases} I_{C h_0} = \frac{W_C T_C^3}{12} + W_C T_C \left(\frac{T_C}{2} + h_0 \right)^2 \\ I_{R h_0} = \frac{W_R T_R^3}{12} + W_R T_R \left(\frac{T_R}{2} - h_0 \right)^2 \end{cases}. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Appendix B. The FEA model for mathematical model validation

The FEA model and raw data for the bending rigidity and linear density of the cross-section for Table 6, as well as the data for the validation of the mathematical model of G_n in Fig. 9 are supplemented. The Abaqus software is used to create a FEA model of a bare cantilever resonator. The mesh element shape used is hexahedron. The FEA model of the bare cantilever is illustrated in Fig. B.1(a). The first five order natural frequencies of the cantilever's bending mode are listed in Table B.1. To verify the accuracy of the mathematical model in accounting for the added bending stiffness to added linear density ratio, the FEA model is created and illustrated in Fig. B.1(b). The first five natural frequencies of the bending mode for different material adsorbates, with either stiffness or mass effect only, are listed in Table B.2. To validate the accuracy of the mathematical model in calculating G_n for an adsorbate located at different positions, the FEA model is illustrated in Fig. B.1(c). The first five natural frequencies of the bending mode for the polymer cube, with either stiffness or mass effect only, are provided in Table B.3. We calculated G_n using both the mathematical and FEA methods, and the results are presented in Table B.4.

The grid-independent study of the FEA models is carried out by using Abaqus software and the results are illustrated in Fig. B.2. The values of mesh elements we used in the simulations are 284 746, 81 600, 42 000, 287 250, and 255 000, respectively. These values of mesh elements are much higher than the minimum elements for mesh-independent in Fig. B.2(a-e).

Table B.2

The simulation of the first-order bending natural frequencies of the cantilever resonator with adsorbates made of different materials are performed using the FEA method.

Material	Stiffness effect (Hz)	Mass effect (Hz)
MCF-7	1.89604×10^5	1.72031×10^5
TMV	2.09479×10^5	1.73885×10^5
E-coli	1.93122×10^5	1.73572×10^5
Myosin	1.92075×10^5	1.85982×10^5
Platinum	4.25708×10^5	8.00970×10^4
Gold	3.45573×10^5	8.35980×10^4
Polymer	1.94368×10^5	1.76027×10^5
Diamond	6.50603×10^5	1.43178×10^5

Table B.3

The natural frequency of the cantilever with a polymer cube located on different locations of it by using FEA.

Adsorbate location	Order	Stiffness effect (Hz)	Mass effect (Hz)
Fixed end	1st	1.92744×10^5	1.89573×10^5
	2nd	1.19550×10^6	1.18381×10^6
	3rd	3.34084×10^6	3.27949×10^6
	4th	6.55037×10^6	6.37208×10^6
	5th	1.08199×10^7	1.05324×10^7
$\chi_m = 1/4$	1st	1.91579×10^5	1.89400×10^5
	2nd	1.19008×10^6	1.16988×10^6
	3rd	3.34609×10^6	3.22010×10^6
	4th	6.54901×10^6	6.35643×10^6
	5th	1.08133×10^7	1.05091×10^7
$\chi_m = 1/2$	1st	1.90147×10^5	1.87739×10^5
	2nd	1.20093×10^6	1.14743×10^6
	3rd	3.33375×10^6	3.28973×10^6
	4th	6.55855×10^6	6.37636×10^6
	5th	1.08193×10^7	1.05231×10^7
$\chi_m = 3/4$	1st	1.89660×10^5	1.83211×10^5
	2nd	1.19316×10^6	1.17956×10^6
	3rd	3.35879×10^6	3.25983×10^6
	4th	6.56381×10^6	6.40174×10^6
	5th	1.08248×10^7	1.05482×10^7
Free end	1st	1.89611×10^5	1.79839×10^5
	2nd	1.18900×10^6	1.16375×10^6
	3rd	3.33740×10^6	3.26476×10^6
	4th	6.55373×10^6	6.36951×10^6
	5th	1.08296×10^7	1.05375×10^7

Table B.4

The G_n obtained by FEA and mathematical model simulation.

Adsorbate location	Order	$G_{n, \text{Math}}$	$G_{n, \text{FEA}}$	Difference
Fixed end	1st	1.15460×10^2	1.05542×10^2	8.59%
	2nd	2.15174	1.85451	13.81%
	3rd	4.53282×10^{-1}	3.49991×10^{-1}	22.79%
	4th	3.38468×10^{-1}	2.74469×10^{-1}	18.91%
	5th	3.24084×10^{-1}	2.85668×10^{-1}	11.85%
$\chi_m = 1/4$	1st	1.08375×10^1	9.76900	9.86%
	2nd	1.51100×10^{-1}	1.18339×10^{-1}	21.68%
	3rd	2.05241×10^{-1}	1.95299×10^{-1}	4.84%
	4th	2.32054×10^{-1}	2.37249×10^{-1}	-2.24%
	5th	2.73776×10^{-1}	2.31578×10^{-1}	15.41%
$\chi_m = 1/2$	1st	3.27837×10^{-1}	2.87961×10^{-1}	12.16%
	2nd	3.27837×10^{-1}	3.07285×10^{-1}	6.27%
	3rd	3.27837×10^{-1}	2.54352×10^{-1}	22.42%
	4th	3.27837×10^{-1}	3.42707×10^{-1}	-4.54%
	5th	3.27834×10^{-1}	2.71304×10^{-1}	17.24%
$\chi_m = 3/4$	1st	9.91710×10^{-3}	8.47030×10^{-3}	14.59%
	2nd	7.11297×10^{-1}	6.25443×10^{-1}	12.07%
	3rd	5.23662×10^{-1}	5.12333×10^{-1}	2.16%
	4th	4.63155×10^{-1}	4.72047×10^{-1}	-1.92%
	5th	3.92572×10^{-1}	3.31435×10^{-1}	15.57%
Free end	1st	9.30871×10^{-4}	7.56620×10^{-4}	18.72%
	2nd	4.99487×10^{-2}	4.41849×10^{-2}	11.54%
	3rd	2.37110×10^{-1}	2.06163×10^{-1}	13.05%
	4th	3.17539×10^{-1}	2.92429×10^{-1}	7.91%
	5th	3.31632×10^{-1}	3.36206×10^{-1}	-1.38%

Fig. B.2. The grid-independent analysis of the FEA models. The dotted lines are the minimum mesh elements required to get grid-independent bending natural frequencies. (a) Bare cantilever. (b) Added stiffness effect with polymeric adsorbate fully covered the cantilever. (c) Added mass effect with polymeric adsorbate fully covered the cantilever. (d) Added stiffness effect with polymeric adsorbate located at the fixed end of the cantilever. (e) Added mass effect with polymeric adsorbate located at the fixed end of the cantilever.

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